

THEORETICAL-METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPING THE KNOWLEDGE OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS ABOUT SPORTS TOURISM

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of the knowledge of the future physical education teachers about tourism are studied. Pedagogical activities related to the improvement of the pedagogue training system at the new stage of development of the society, introduction of innovative approaches to it, and the creation of productive principles and models of training specialists were also analyzed.

Key words: physical education, sport, tourism, sports tourism, professional activity, training, component, empirical, pedagogical feature, methodology.

INTRODUCTION. Today, at the new stage of development of the society, the pedagogical activity of improving the system of training pedagogues, bringing innovative approaches to it, and thereby creating productive principles and models of training specialists is considered a priority task. This process is recognized by certain ideas in pedagogical education, which are related to the general laws of the development of modern society. Therefore, introducing new ideas, theories and approaches to the personnel training system is becoming urgent.

A unique, healthy lifestyle culture based on economic, social, political and spiritual aspects is forming in our country. A component of this culture is associated with various activities. An important factor determining such development is a healthy cultural life, the health of the nation within it. The importance of fitness training in maintaining health, which is considered wealth, is immeasurable.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Many studies have been conducted on the development of the professional skills of physical education and sports specialists, and the effective organization of the formation of moral values in athletes. aspects of mental, functional preparation; N.N. Tokhtaboyev, A.N. Shopulatov, S.S. Tajibayev, F. Kerimov, R. Abdumalikov, A. Muzaffarov, A. Mirzayev, A. Khudoyorov conducted research on improving the training of sports professionals using action games.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. According to our point of view, fitness training with its essence has a worthy place in the structure of physical culture as a tool, preparing the body of society members for daily life activities, creating the necessary biological strength for this activity and refers to their use in the process of mental and physical work. These trainings are different from targeted training during human life activity. In its current definition, the physical culture of a healthy lifestyle and its activities serve as one of the leading tools in the implementation of the education of a well-rounded generation.

Nowadays, one of the important tasks of educational institutions is to teach pupils and students to engage in physical education and sports in order to grow up physically healthy. The term "health care" is now gaining a very broad meaning, its modern meaning is understood not only in the sense of health, but also in the comprehensively developed and

highly practical and quality of physical performance, from learning to quickly adapt to a changing climate. can be interpreted as consisting of This age of technical progress requires a person to be able to skillfully manage movement quickly, and to have thorough physical training. The foundation for all these things is laid from a young age. Also, "physical training and sports lead to comprehensive physical development and strengthening of the human body, improvement of physiological functions and health. Properly organized physical training sessions, taking into account the age, gender and specific characteristics of the participants, are highly effective. Otherwise, they will lose the importance of physical education in solving the health problem" [4]. Therefore, in the process of physical education and upbringing, the main emphasis will be on the formation of a healthy lifestyle in society.

According to the concept of development of physical education and mass sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan, "active development of physical education and sports, involvement of all strata of the population, especially young people, to regularly engage in physical education and mass sports, benefits of a healthy lifestyle in society and to widely promote the superiority, to ensure the full and effective use of the physical education-health and sports infrastructure created in the country" [2] is indicated as the main goal. In this way, the main tasks of physical education of students are as follows: To help strengthen health, exercise, all-round harmonious and physical development, increase the quality of mental and physical work. The tasks of fitness, physical development and the formation of movement skills and abilities are in different forms depending on the age, gender and personal characteristics of those engaged in physical education and sports. Physical education of students is aimed at their harmonious physical development and training of the body, while playing sports is aimed at achieving specialization in sports and showing high results in sports. Also, the age, gender, physical fitness, health, and interests of those involved in physical education and sports play an important role in the implementation of physical education.

Decree No. PF-5924 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2020 "On measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" It is noted that many measures are being taken to promote a healthy lifestyle, to create the necessary conditions for the physical rehabilitation of persons with limited capabilities, and to ensure the appropriate participation of the country in international sports arenas. implementation of specific programs that help to strengthen the health of the population in the field of sports, wide involvement of young people in sports and the selection of talented athletes from among them, the formation of national teams with skilled athletes who provide high results in sports, and for trainers the need to create additional conditions" [1] was also highlighted. Through this, the tasks of improving the health of the society, establishing a healthy lifestyle in people, increasing the physical capabilities of young people and focusing on self-expression through sports are gaining priority.

For this, it is necessary to improve the training system of future physical education teachers, introduce new approaches to it, develop innovative foundations, as well as study the experience of developed countries in physical education and training, integrate them into national education, differentiate Based on the approach, developing a methodology for effective work with students for future physical education teachers, testing educational technology to increase their knowledge and skills to positively influence their psyche is one of the important tasks for pedagogical research. remains one.

The following scientific studies served as a methodological basis for our research aimed at developing knowledge of sports tourism among future physical education teachers:

The thesis of the research work "Sport tourism" [3] carried out by the team of M. Gazalova, A. Schikanov, A. Vernigor, V. Bagdasarian served as an important theoretical basis. It analyzes the formation of sports tourism, its classification and training areas, the possibilities of tourist places for extreme sports, the development of sports tourism, and the socio-economic efficiency of attracting young people to sports tourism.

Also, the monograph "Sport-health tourism" [6] by Y. Fedotov and I. Vostokov serves as an important source for researching the theoretical foundations of sports tourism. Researchers divide sports tourism into two directions: sports health tourism and active sports tourism. It is stated that sports tourism is aimed at maintaining inactive health and restoring health. The main essence of the monograph is the types, directions and opportunities of sports tourism as a type of activity aimed at health promotion and health care.

Also, the research work "theory and methodology of sports tourism" [5] by research scientist Y. Fedotov is an important methodical guide to sports tourism. It describes the problems of training athletes, the problems that have a negative impact on the development of sports tourism, the possibilities and social importance of sports tourism, and the methodology and theoretical foundations of sports tourism education. This source serves as an important methodological basis for the development of knowledge about sports tourism in future personnel.

Researching the pedagogical possibilities of developing the knowledge of tourism and sports tourism of future physical education teachers, its necessity, pedagogical foundations, methodological system and pedagogical-psychological principles, in general, knowledge of sports tourism based on the study of theoretical and methodological foundations to create a harmony of active activity and motivation for success in development, and on the basis of this, to guide the acquisition of knowledge about sports tourism, to make quick decisions in difficult situations based on the study of types of sports tourism and extreme sports, to form sports-specific qualities while quickly adapting to situations to achieve, in this process, the possibilities of knowledge growth based on the gradual formation of the functional aspects of organizing the process of acquiring knowledge and learning activities, taking into account the volitional, emotional attitude towards the external environment and motivational tools, were clarified.

The current development of science, technology, production and technology spheres determines the image of modern society. "The most important feature of the modern society is that globalization is visible in all its spheres. Globalization itself requires rapid movement, immediate acquisition of necessary information, their processing and effective implementation. Only personnel who are knowledgeable in their field, have acquired professional skills at a high level, and have rich experience and skills will have the opportunity to move in this way" [4]. Therefore, it is appropriate to take into account this demand of the time in the process of training personnel in higher education institutions.

CONCLUSION. From the theoretical analysis of the literature, it can be seen that physical education as an education attracts the attention of all experts in the world, as well as its description (expression of content and essence) and classification (means, application processes) scientists express in their own way. Based on this, it can be said that physical education is a pedagogical process aimed at improving the human body morphologically and

functionally, forming and improving basic movement skills, skills, and related knowledge that are important for his life. . This description can be recognized as reasonable when used in the language of science.

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